

Quantum Effects of a Single Particle Bound State

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A classical bound state does indicate the direction of motion if one only considers kinetic energy $pp/2m$. It is the vector quantities, p and x , which indicate direction. In quantum mechanics, a free particle interaction probability (for impulse hits) is directional, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ not $\exp(-ipx)$. Unless one has a single value of $pp/2m$, $KE = \sum_{p>0} a(p)\exp(ipx) pp/2m / \sum_{p>0} a(p)\exp(ipx)$ is not equal to KE^- even if $a(p)=a(-p)$. In order to use conservation of energy in quantum mechanics, one is forced to consider both $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(p)\exp(-ipx)$ with $a(p)=a(-p)$ which is the correct statistical weighting for a bound state. One may note that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability for interaction and is separate from $x=p/m t$ even though the notion of this velocity is tied to the fact that nonrelativistic kinetic energy is $pp/2m$. As a result, one must use an average scenario for calculating kinetic energy which seems to be tied to an ensemble average. Such a notion should hold for all energy levels.

If one considers the classical limit, then one has $p(x)p(x)/2m$ in a tiny dx . If one were to simply use $1/\sqrt{p}\exp(ip(x) x)/\sqrt{dx}$ in dx , then $\int W^*W dx$ in $dx = C/p$. The relative weight of two adjacent dx regions is: $p_1/p_2 = p_1 / (p_1+dp)$. This is equivalent to probabilities proportional to $dt = dx/v$, where $p=mv$. Thus, the area represented by W^*W captures the number of possible interactions in dx if attempted hits have a fixed period. We argue, however, that given the bound state conservation recipe, one must use $a(p) (\exp(ipx)+\exp(-ipx))$ to describe a dx (with $p=p(x)$), even in the high energy limit. $\exp(ipx)$ is simply an interaction pattern (and is a probability) and so if the particle is bound, the correct statistical thing to do for an ensemble seems to be to combine $\exp(ipx)$ with $\exp(-ipx)$. We then show that quantum mechanics lowers the number of interactions in an area with increased speed more than the classical case. In particular, we find instead of $p/(p+dp)$, $1 - dp/p - 2dp/(pp)$.

Kinetic Energy in Classical and Quantum Mechanics

A classical free nonrelativistic particle moves as:

$$x=vt \quad p=mv \quad KE=pp/2m \quad ((1))$$

A quantum free nonrelativistic particle moves as:

$$x=vt \quad p=mv \quad KE=pp/2m \quad \text{probability for impulse hit}=\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

We argue that a quantum particle is associated with both deterministic classical motion $x=vt$, $p=vm$, $KE=pp/2m$, but also with a stochastic probability $\exp(ipx)$ for hits. We note that one cannot arrive at $pp/2m$ without using $dx=v dt$. As a result, both classical and probabilistic ideas are present in quantum mechanics which makes the interpretation of $\exp(ipx)$ unusual. We suggest that it is a probability (and so one must respect ideas of statistics), but only for impulse hits in space. Given that an interaction requires impulse hits, $\exp(ipx)$ may be used to average classical values such as p and $pp/2m$ at any energy level.

What is unusual is that for a classical bound particle $p = 0$, but for a quantum particle $p = \hbar \exp(ipx) - \hbar \exp(-ipx) \neq 0$. Similarly, if one uses more than one $\exp(ipx)$ to calculate average kinetic energy:

$$\text{Sum over } p > 0 \quad p^2/2m \cdot a(p)\exp(ipx) / \text{Sum over } p > 0 \quad a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad \text{not=}$$

$$\text{Sum over } p < 0 \quad p^2/2m \cdot a(p)\exp(ipx) / \text{Sum over } p < 0 \quad a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

Unlike in classical physics, the average kinetic energy is not the same for forwards and backwards motion. This seems strange, but one does not calculate average kinetic energy simply using $p^2/2m$, but must use the directional probability $\exp(ipx)$. Given the statistical nature of the problem, one should consider both $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ because only choosing one breaks the symmetry of the bound problem. If a quantum particle only moves in one direction, then $\exp(ipx)$ (or $\exp(-ipx)$) is fine, but not for a bound problem, we argue. This seems to be compatible with the statistical nature of the problem. To argue that a particle at high energy moves first to the right and then to the left is correct, but this is the deterministic feature of the problem. In terms of interaction probabilities, one uses $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ as interaction probability patterns in space for a bound problem. In other words, one is not following the physical particle in space. $\exp(ipx)$ represents a probability pattern (with x representing a fluctuation) and not the x of $x=vt$.

We suggest that this idea means that quantum mechanics affects the probability to interact with a particle in a different manner than the classical result.

Classical and Quantum Probabilities to Interact

Traditionally, $W^*(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction) is said to represent the probability to find a particle at x . We argue that given that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability for impulse hit, $W^*(x)W(x)$ is only the probability to have an impulse hit at x . Even in $W^*(x)W(x)=0$, a particle may be present at this point, it just does not deliver an impulse hit. $x=vt$ still holds for a constant speed. As a result, if one has two adjacent dx regions, one may integrate

$$\text{Integral } dx \quad W^*(x)W(x) \text{ region 1} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Integral } dx \quad W^*(x)W(x) \text{ region 2} \quad ((4))$$

Taking the ratio 2 to 1 shows the ratio of impulse hits, i.e. interactions. One may ask whether this may be linked to classical physics. In the literature, one sometimes sees that statement that for a bound problem with constant dx units:

$$dt = dx/v \quad \text{proportional to a probability} \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is promoted as a probability to find a particle in dx , but we argue that one can only “find” a particle if one interacts with it. As a result, this seems to mean that one sends periodic hits into each piece of dx and sees how many collisions with the particle occur. If the particle moves fast, there will be fewer hits. Thus, ((5)) holds.

To find a quantum analogue which yields ((5)), one may consider the wavefunction:

$$W(x) = C \frac{1}{\sqrt{p_1}} \exp(i p(x_1) x_1) \text{ (for } dx \text{ about } x=x_1, 0 \text{ elsewhere)} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{p_2}} C \exp(i p(x_2) x_2) \text{ (for } dx \text{ about } x=x_2, 0 \text{ elsewhere)} + \dots \quad ((5))$$

Then $W^*(x)W(x)$ for x_1 is proportional to 1 and the integral becomes $1/\sqrt{p}$ Integral $dx W^*(p_1 x)W(p_1 x)$.

The ratio of interaction hits is: $p_1/p_2 \quad ((6))$

One may note that one is forced to use the weighting $1/\sqrt{p}$ in ((5)) in order to obtain the classical result which seems artificial. This already seems to point to the idea that using unidirectional $\exp(ipx)$ is problematic.

If $p_2=p_1+dp_1$, then $p_1/p_2 = 1 - dp_1/p_1 \quad ((7))$

The problem with ((5)) is that it does not represent the statistics of a bound state, i.e. it breaks symmetry. A bound state must have $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$.

We first consider the following. At x_1 , the classical kinetic energy is $p(x_1)p(x_1)/2m$.

((5)) yields $p(x_1)p(x_1)/2m \exp(i p(x_1) x_1) / \exp(i p(x_1) x_1) \quad ((8))$

If one considers $\exp(ip(x_1)x_1) + \exp(-i p(x_1)x_1)$, then:

$$pp_2/m \{ \exp(ip(x_1)x_1) + \exp(-i p(x_1)x_1) \} / \{ \exp(ip(x_1)x_1) + \exp(-i p(x_1)x_1) \} = pp_2/m \quad ((9))$$

Thus, one does have $p(x_1)p(x_1)/2m$ at x_1 .

The difference arises in the number of impulse hits.

Integral $(0,L) dx \cos(p_1 x) \cos(p_1 x) dx$ versus Integral $(L, 2L) \cos(p_2 x) \cos(p_2 x) dx \quad ((10))$

Integral $dy \cos(y) \cos(y) = y/2 + \sin(2y)/4 \quad ((11))$

If one chooses $2p_1L=0$ and $p_2=p_1+dp_1$ then:

Number of hits in $(0,L)$ proportional to $1/p_1 (p_1L/2) \quad ((11a))$

Number of hits in $(L, 2L)$ proportional to $1/p_2 (p_1L/2 + dp_1/2 + dp_1 L - dp_1 L /2)$

Taking the ratio: $p_2 \text{ hits} / p_1 \text{ hits} = p_1/(p_1+dp_1) (1 + dp_1 L / p_1) = 1 - dp_1/p - 2dp_1 L / (p_1 p_1) \quad ((12))$

The first two terms of ((12)) match the classical value, but $-2dp_1/(p_1^2)$ decreases the number of hits in the region of the faster speed. There are even fewer hits in the faster region according to quantum mechanics, it seems. We suggest, however, that this only occurs if one uses $\exp(ipx)+\exp(-ipx)$ in a dx and not $\exp(ipx)$ which is uni-directional. Thus, there seems to be a special statistical requirement for bound state calculations even though one is tempted to use $\exp(ipx)$ for motion the right and $\exp(-ipx)$ for motion to the left. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ represent interaction probability patterns in space and should not be linked to time, i.e. $x=vt$ motion. The full form is $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and neither t nor x are the same t , or x in $x=vt$. They are fluctuations variables showing the probability of interactions, we argue.

Conclusion

We argue that quantum mechanics makes use of purely classical ideas like $x=vt$, $p=mv$ and $pp/2m = \text{kinetic energy}$. In particular, $ke=pp/2m$ makes use of $dx=vdt$. (These are nonrelativistic results.) The quantum feature arises in $\exp(ipx)$ which is a probability for an impulse hit to occur at x . This x is not to be thought of as x in $x=vt$, but rather there is a probability pattern in space. For a bound particle, classically it moves to the right and then to the left, but statistically one does not follow this motion. Rather there is probability to the right and left and they must be added $\exp(ipx)+\exp(-ipx)$ for $a(p)=a(-p)$. It is this probability that is used to calculate average kinetic energy which is then used in a conservation of energy equation.

We argue that in the classical limit, a particle moves to the right and then to the left, but this is $x=vt$ type of motion, not a quantum effect. One might try to mimic this for high energy using $W(x) = 1/\sqrt{p_1} \exp(ip_1 x_1)$ (dx about x_1 , 0 elsewhere) + $1/\sqrt{p_2} \exp(ip_2 x_2)$ (dx about x_2 , 0 elsewhere) +..... This yields $W^*W = 1$ in each dx and so $1/p \int dx \exp(ipx)\exp(ipx)$ in a dx . This would yield the classical $dt^2/dt^1 = p_1/p_2 = p_1/(p_1+dp_1)$ result. We argue, however, that quantum mechanically one should use $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ because one is dealing with probabilities linked to a bound state. One is not following the particle through $x = v(x) t$ and cannot apply this kind of reasoning to the probabilities. This approach then leads to the ratio $p_1/(p_1+dp_1) (1+dp_1^2/p_1) = 1-dp_1/p - 2dp_1/(p_1^2)$ which decreases the number of hits in the faster region $-2dp_1/(p_1^2)$ than the classical result.